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FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF TOPICAL MICROSPONGE BASED GEL OF TURMERIC

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ABSTRACT

A drug delivery system enables the introduction of a therapeutic substance in the body and improves its efficacy and safety by controlling the rate, time and place of release of drug in the body. One of these includes topical preparations. These are used for localized effect at the site of their application^[3, 4]. A new method approached in TDDS is microsponge. Microsponge drug delivery system is a patented, higher cross linked porous, polymeric microsponge that can entrap wide range of activities and release them with desired rate^[3, 4]. With lots of synthetic and inorganic drugs used in the market for treatment of various diseases; natural drugs have also gained appreciation and still has high market demand even today. Natural drug helps by reducing toxicity and any adverse drug effects and thus adding for better pharmacological effect. Curcumin which is active ingredient obtained from the powdered dry rhizomes of the plant *Curcuma longa* (which is commonly called turmeric). It is widely used as a colouring agent, medicinal agent and as a spice in many food items. It also can be used for treatment for conditions ranging from flatulence, jaundice, hepatitis, pains and haemorrhage^[5]. An approach is being made in combining the old tradition with the new technology to gain more appreciation in the market. This leads to the formulation of “Gel Loaded Turmeric Microsponge” as a Novel Drug Delivery.

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INTRODUCTION

Drug Delivery System:

A drug delivery system enables the introduction of a therapeutic substance in the body and improves its efficacy and safety by controlling the rate, time and place of release of drug in the body. An ideal drug delivery system should deliver the drug at the rate dictated by the needs of the body over the period of treatment.

The preparation and evaluation of gel containing turmeric microsp sponge which is a topical dosage form and it shows therapeutic activity as an anti-inflammatory.

Introduction to Turmeric:

Turmeric is a product of *Curcuma longa*, a rhizomatous herbaceous perennial plant belonging to the ginger family Zingiberaceae, which is native to tropical South Asia. As many as 133 species of *Curcuma* have been identified worldwide. The main component of the root is a volatile oil, containing turmerone, and there are other colouring agents called curcuminoids in turmeric. Curcuminoids consist of curcumin demethoxycurcumin, 5'-methoxycurcumin, and dihydrocurcumin, which are found to be natural antioxidants. Curcumin which is the active ingredient is obtained from the powdered dry rhizome of the plant *Curcuma longa*, commonly called turmeric is widely used as a colouring agent, medicinal agent and as spice in many food items. It contains wide variety of phytochemicals including curcumin, curcumol, eugenol, turmerones, zingiberene, etc ^[5, 8].

Introduction to Topical Drug Delivery System:

Topical preparations are used for localized effect at the site of their application by virtue of drug penetration into the underlying layers of skin or mucous membrane. It includes two basic types:

External topical that are spread, sprayed or otherwise dispersed on to cutaneous tissues to cover the affected area.

Internal topical that are applied to the mucous membrane orally, vaginally or on anorectal tissues for local activity.

Microsp sponge drug delivery system is a patented, highly cross linked, porous, polymeric microsp sponge that can entrap wide range of actives and release them with desired rate. This system is applicable for the improvement of performance of topically applied drugs. It is a unique technology for controlled release of topical agents and consists of micro porous beads.

Advantages of microsp sponge drug delivery over the drug delivery system:

- Microspheres cannot usually control the release rate of actives. Once the wall is ruptured the activity contained within the microspheres will be released
- The amount released from the microsp sponge is programmable.
- The rate of release mechanism depends on the pressure, volatility, temperature, solvent, partition coefficient ^[7].

METHODOLOGY

Formulation development of microsp sponge

The drug was incorporated in a novel micro particulate microsp sponge system having a drug dispersed matrix. The selection of a particular encapsulation method is primarily determined by the solubility characteristics of the drug and polymer. The method should ideally produce (a) high yields of micro particles and free of extensive agglomeration, (b) appropriate encapsulation of the core material.

Methodology for formulating curcumin microsp sponge

Microsponges were prepared by Quasi Emulsion Solvent Diffusion Technique which requires two immiscible phases internal and external phase with a surfactant which aids formation of an emulsion by reducing the interfacial tension. The method consists of two steps. In the first step inner phase was prepared and in second step outer phase was prepared.

Ingredients used:

Drug	: curcumin
Polymer	: ethyl cellulose
Solvent	: dichloromethane
Glycerol	: plasticity
External phase	: polyvinyl alcohol

QUASI EMULSION TECHNIQUE

FORMULATION TABLE – MICROSPONGE.

SR.NO	INGREDIENTS	QUANTITY TAKEN
1	Turmeric	1g
2	Ethyl cellulose	1g
3	Polyvinyl alcohol (5%)	20ml
4	Dichloromethane	10ml
5	Glycerol	1ml
6	Water	100ml

STEP 1: Preparation of inner phase.

DIAGRAM:

Fig1: Quasi Emulsion Diffusion Technique.

2.4: FORMULATION TABLE – GEL.

SR.NO	INGREDIENTS	QUANTITY
1.	Carbopol	Equivalent to microsponge
2.	Water	100 times that of microsponge
3.	Triethanolamine	Quantity sufficient
4.	Glycerine	Quantity sufficient

STEP 4: Preparation of Gel.

DISCUSSION AND RESULT

An approach was being made in combining the old tradition with the new technology leading to the formulation of a novel drug delivery system –“gel loaded turmeric microsponges” as an anti –inflammatory.

Firstly, turmeric microsponges were prepared by quasi emulsion solvent diffusion technique. Various ratios of drug: Polymers were analyzed but 1:1 gave required type of micro sponge and was found to be stable. These microsponges were then checked for their porous nature, appearance, uniformity in size.

After the formulation for microsponges were complete, they were loaded into the gel. The gelling agents used here is carbopol. The gel was loaded with turmeric microsponges by the basic gel formulation process.

The gel formulation was then checked for the appearance, consistency of the gel

Following are the evaluations carried out:

- Appearance
- Consistency- semisolid
- Odour- pleasant
- Colour-white coloured gel loaded with yellow colour turmeric microsponges
- Spreadibility- easily spreadable
- pH- neural

UV spectroscopy –

For the determination of the percentage of turmeric entrapped in the micro sponge, UV spectroscopy technique was used. The method consisted of obtaining the spectra of the pure turmeric and of gel loaded micro sponge^[2]. The calibration curve obtained by these two were matched which, drew to a conclusion that the entrapment of turmeric was established in the micro sponge.

The calibration curve obtained for turmeric is as follows:

Concentration of turmeric	Absorbance(at 421nm)
1ppm	0.043
2ppm	0.049
4ppm	0.057
6ppm	0.061
8ppm	0.071
10ppm	0.09

Fig 2: Calibration Curve of Turmeric.

CALIBRATION CURVE OF GEL:

Concentration in ppm	Absorbance(at 421nm)
1	0.022
2	0.046
4	0.106
6	0.169
8	0.187
10	0.232

Fig 3: Calibration Curve of Gel loaded turmeric microspunge.

CONCLUSION

The purpose of present research work was to develop a topical turmeric loaded microspunge based anti inflammatory gel formulation. It has improved the efficacy and safety of turmeric that may be better administered through skin. A controlled release drug delivery system aims for a prolonged period so that can satisfy the goals of the reduction in inflammation.

The need of the hour is design a topical drug delivery system of turmeric that could not only increase the presence of the drug locally and for a prolonged period, but also reduce the risk of toxicity.

Microsponges were prepared by Quasi Emulsion Solvent Diffusion Technique. These microsponges are then loaded into the gel for getting gel loaded turmeric microspunge. Formed microsponges were evaluated for pH, particle size distribution, spreadability, UV absorbance. Calibration curves of drug were constructed by UV Vis spectrophotometer.

The said formulation was found to be non irritant to the skin, providing cooling effect thus adding to the anti-inflammatory action. To conclude the formulation was found to be giving anti-inflammatory action along with sustain release of the drug.

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